

PROFESSIONAL TERMS IN THE LANGUAGE SYSTEM: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NATIONAL LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются термины профессиональной лексики ножеделия, их лингвокультурные и лингвоареальные языковые характеристики.

Ключевые слова: язык и культура, национальный язык, литературный язык, профессиональная лексика, диалектные ареалы, нож и узбекские термины ножеделия.

Annotation. The article examines the terms of professional vocabulary of knifemaking, their linguacultural and linguaareal language characteristics.

Key words: language and culture, national language, literary language, professional vocabulary, dialect areas, knife and Uzbek terms of knifemaking.

In world linguistics, increasing emphasis is being placed on studying language in connection with the individual speaker, their unique national and spiritual world, and lifestyle. As a result of such approaches to language study, by the mid-20th century, the scope of linguistic research expanded, giving rise to new fields such as ethnolinguistics, linguoculturology, and anthropocentric analysis. These fields opened up opportunities to explore new aspects of language related to the human world. Consequently, studying language in organic connection with the historical development, lifestyle, daily life, traditional culture, and spiritual world of the people who speak it has become one of the key issues in linguistics.

In global linguistics, language tools are regarded as a crucial factor reflecting the customs and traditions of each nation, expressing its national identity, and defining its spirituality. It is well known that every national language has unique lexical units with distinct meanings and content, which are studied in relation to the people's culture, spiritual values, distinctive way of thinking, and national-historical traditions. This approach is of great importance and underscores the relevance of such research.

In Uzbek linguistics, there is growing interest in studying the language in connection with the customs, historical traditions, spiritual world, and occupations of the Uzbek people. This is because "preserving, studying, and passing down historical heritage to future generations is one of the most

important priorities of our state's policy¹. As every nation possesses common characteristics, it also has unique traits, and such distinctiveness is considered the customs and traditions of a particular nation.

At present, Uzbek terminology is developing rapidly in all directions. Fundamental concepts related to science, technology, politics, economics, and cultural life are supported by a proportionate terminology system. During the years of independence, a variety of bilingual, multilingual, and explanatory dictionaries have been published in the country. Currently, intensive work is being carried out to compile terminological dictionaries for various fields, and educational, methodological, and scientific literature related to terminology is being published. The role of mass media is significant in the further development of Uzbek terminology. The main source of enrichment, expansion, and improvement of the modern Uzbek literary language's terminological system, as is the case in other languages, is undoubtedly its own lexical wealth. The development of Uzbek terminology based on its own resources and capabilities occurs in two ways: a) using existing words in the language to express new objects, concepts, or phenomena; b) creating new terms through the word-formation possibilities of the Uzbek literary language. Morphological, semantic, and syntactic methods of word formation are effectively used in creating new terms. The method of calquing also plays a noticeable role in term creation. A significant portion of Uzbek terminology consists of terms derived from the Russian-international lexical fund. Terms borrowed from other non-Turkic languages are characterized by encompassing the social, political, economic, cultural, and spiritual aspects of the Uzbek people's activities.

During the period of former Soviet rule, many ancient words that played a significant role in the formation and development of the Uzbek language's lexicon were unjustly categorized as outdated lexical units, i.e., archaisms. Rectifying this injustice and restoring historical truth were prioritized as important tasks. Due to the absence of equivalents for certain concepts in the Uzbek terminology system, the ability to express them with a single word is limited.

The lexicon of professions is an important aspect that determines the ethnographic distinctiveness of a particular ethnos, and its expression through linguistic means is of great significance for both linguistics and ethnography. Each region has its own ethnographic lexicon, and collecting and studying it from a linguistic perspective, as well as passing it down from generation to

generation as a linguistic tool, creates opportunities to address many linguistic challenges.

Culture is the expression of a person's inner and outer world, their way of thinking, and their manner of conveying thoughts and ideas to others. Since ancient times, a person's identity has been defined by their manners, ethics, and linguistic culture. Culture is a multifaceted concept.

According to the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language," it is used in five different senses². However, culture in the sense of literacy, education, enlightenment, and intellectual refinement emerges as a result of a person's linguistic activity. Thus, culture is connected to language, and this connection has been recognized in linguistics, leading to the emergence of linguoculturology the science of linguistic culture at the intersection of language and culture.

For linguoculturology, studying culture is considered more important than studying progress, as progress is material, while culture is symbolic. Myths, traditions, and rituals are inherent to culture, reflected in the lifestyle and ceremonies of a people through linguistic units and expressions. For this reason, these linguistic units are considered objects of study in linguoculturology. By the early 20th century, linguoculturology had become one of the leading directions in global linguistics. As emphasized in numerous linguistic studies, "linguoculturology is a science that studies language as a cultural phenomenon, with the interconnectedness of language and culture forming its subject matter"³. V.N. Teliya writes about this as follows: "Linguoculturology is a science that studies the human, or more precisely, the personality and cultural factors in their interconnectedness."⁴.

According to G. Slisshkin, "Linguoculturology is oriented toward the human factor and the cultural factor within a person, and the fact that its core consists of the cultural phenomenon indicates that it pertains to the anthropological paradigm of the science of humanity."⁵.

N. Mahmudov writes the following about language and culture, which are among the most fundamental concepts in the field: "When we talk about language and culture, the issue of 'speech culture' often comes to mind associatively, but this does not truly reflect the essence of culture in these two contexts. When referring to language and culture, it is generally (and rightly so) understood as explaining a particular culture through language or, conversely,

understanding a language through the study of a culture. To put it more precisely, the meaning of culture in linguoculturology is not 'the level or degree achieved in intellectual-spiritual or economic activity (speech culture)' but rather 'the sum of achievements acquired in the productive, social, and intellectual-spiritual life of human society (cultural history, Uzbek culture).' Therefore, the issues of studying speech culture are distinct, while the object of study in linguoculturology is entirely different"⁶.

Language is one of the most important indicators of culture, as a person's worldview, culture, and spirituality are formed and expressed through language. At the same time, language is not only a means of communication between people but also an environment that shapes a person's life experience, where they are formed and live. It can even be said that a person seemingly lives within language and constantly experiences its influence⁷.

The language reflects a person's unique worldview and culture. Its most important function is to preserve culture and pass it from generation to generation. Therefore, language plays a significant role in shaping personality, national character, people, and nation.

The relationship between language and culture, as well as their mutual influence, is a subject of study for many specialists: cultural scholars, linguists, and philosophers. Accordingly, it can be said that linguoculturology is a highly complex and multifaceted field.

For over a century, the issue of the relationship between language and culture has occupied the minds of numerous researchers and scholars, yet it remains a debated topic to this day. Attempts to define language through culture and culture through language testify to their mutual interdependence and interaction: language does not exist outside of culture, and culture cannot exist without language.

Language grows, develops, and expresses itself in connection with culture, embodying the uniqueness of a people, their national culture, and the distinct national worldview of each nation. For example, we can cite the words of two prominent scholars, the founders of the American and European ethnolinguistic schools.

The most prominent representative of this approach is Wilhelm von Humboldt, whose main ideas are summarized as follows:

- 1) Material and spiritual culture are embodied in language;

2) Every culture is national, and its national character is expressed in language through a unique worldview; each nation's language has its own distinct internal form;

3) The internal form of language is the "national spirit," which is an expression of a people's culture;

4) Language is a means of connection between a person and the world around them⁸. V. Humboldt's approach was also uniquely interpreted in the works of his follower A.A. Potebnya. Language is considered both a product or part of culture (inherited from ancestors) and a condition of culture (through which culture is assimilated). Language is an integral part of culture and its tool, while simultaneously expressing the unique characteristics of national mentality⁹. Attempts to define language through culture and culture through language testify to a mutual interdependence and interaction: language does not exist outside of culture, and culture does not exist without language. They (language and culture) are closely interconnected.

Language penetrates culture, develops within it, and expresses it, embodying the uniqueness of a people, their national culture, and their national worldview. The distinctiveness of a language is shaped by culture, mentality, and the "spirit of the people"¹⁰. Translation scholars emphasize the cultural and linguistic unity of representatives of a specific ethnic group, highlighting their interconnectedness and expressing ideas such as "the unique language of culture" and "language as a carrier of culture." Thus, they combine these crucial indicators of an ethnic group. Additionally, they note that language, as a subject of interpersonal communication, is also a unifying element of culture¹¹. Culture is a phenomenon that is not biologically inherent to humans and is created as a result of people's life activities¹². According to this, every nation has a culture connected to its traditions and way of life, which is primarily reflected in its language. The interdependence of language and culture is determined by the fact that both are natural phenomena. Like language, culture is ancient and gives rise to the unique ethnoculture of each ethnic group. Ethnoculture, in turn, is a collection of assimilated forms aimed at preserving the distinctive characteristics of a particular ethnic group¹³.

In summary, the terminological system of the Uzbek language develops through both internal and external sources. The internal capabilities of the language play a primary role in the development, formation, and improvement of its terminological systems. This is because significant changes in life, as well as advancements in science, technology, and culture, necessitate the maximum utilization of the language's internal resources.

If a term or its expression is not precise and clear, it inevitably leads to confusion and ambiguity. Therefore, the progress of any field or discipline is partly determined by whether its terminology constitutes a "strictly scientific terminology."

Due to the failure to fully adhere to the necessary stages in the creation of over 30 small-scale terminological dictionaries published by the Terminology Committee, or the more than 20 terminological dictionaries of various sizes discussed, approved, and published by different sections of the Committee, these dictionaries contain, to varying degrees, inconsistent (doublet, polysemous, or unclear) terms.

In the Uzbek language, numerous terminological dictionaries in various fields are being compiled by scientific institutions, higher education establishments, publishing houses, and initiative groups regarding nomenclature and its characteristics. However, regulating Uzbek terminology can only be achieved if these dictionaries are developed under the supervision of responsible scientists, scholars, and high-ranking state and administrative officials appointed to oversee the process.

For the study of the professional and occupational lexicon of the Uzbek language, alongside Mahmud Kashgari's *Devoni Lug'otit Turk*, the work of the eminent Uzbek linguist, Honored Scientist of Uzbekistan, Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor Sobirjon Ibrahimov, titled *The Professional Lexicon of the Fergana Dialects*, serves as a foundational resource for studying the lexical layer related to professions and occupations in the Uzbek language.

List of used literature:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will continue our national development path with determination and take it to a new level. Volume I.– Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2017. – P.29.
2. Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. Volume II: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: 2006. – P.521. 93
3. Usmonova Sh. Linguistic and cultural aspects of translation. – Tashkent: 2015. – P.31.
4. Telia V.N. Russian phraseology. – M.:1982. – P. 20-25.

5. Makhmudov N. In search of ways to improve the study of the language // Uzbek language and literature. – Tashkent, 2012. - No. 5. – P. 10 94.
6. Maslova V. A. Linguistics: Textbook. Textbook for students of higher education, institutions. – M.: Publishing center "Academy", 2001. – 208 p.
7. Sabitova Z.K. Linguistics: textbook. – M.: Flint: Nauka, 2013. – 528 p. 96.
8. Ashirov A. Ethnology. New edition. – Tashkent: 2014. – P.171. 543 p.

